

**Some Observations on the Properdin System: Part VII.
Chemical Characterisation of Properdin in relation to
its activity Reveals that it contains no Tyrosine
in its Polypeptide Moiety**

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(with assistance from P. D. Mathur†)

Analysis of different fractions of blood serum exhibiting the biological characteristics of properdin (P) have been carried out with a view to correlating their chemical characteristics and biological activities. The nitrogen, carbon, hydrogen, sulfur and phosphorus contents did not differ much. Although the carbohydrate, hexose, hexosamine and amino-acid nitrogen contents were also nearly equal in different samples, an attempt has been made to correlate the small differences observed in proportions of these components with the activities of the samples. Chromatographic studies of the carbohydrates, lipids and amino-acids of the different samples have been reported. The analysis of the different constituents suggest at present that properdin may be characterised as a lipid-containing glycoprotein of blood serum, whose polypeptide moiety is unique in having no tyrosine in it.

In a previous communication¹ it was reported that the different protein fractions could be isolated from a sample of buffalo blood serum at the isoelectric pH 5.7 of P and that their biological activities differed when assayed by the method described earlier². It was also recorded that more material precipitated with increase in the volume of the dilute acid added¹. However, the pH of the serum was maintained at 5.7 even with the addition of nine volumes of acid, beyond which the precipitate was found to dissolve.

The biological activity of the most potent preparation was found to differ from that of the sample of P prepared by the method of Pillimer when assayed by different methods². It was also observed that the different fractions possessing variable activity are isoelectric in nature.

Some attempts at chemical characterisation of P have been recorded in the earlier literature³. As the sources and methods of isolation of P were different from those used by the present authors, it was felt necessary to investigate the chemical constituents of P obtained by our method of isoelectric precipitation¹ in order to throw some light on the relationship between chemical composition and activity among the different fractions obtained.

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1. A. C. Majumdar and R. Sen, *Indian J. Biochem.*, 1965, **2**, 123.
2. A. C. Majumdar, R. Sen and B. Mukherjee, *Ann. Biochem. Exp. Med.*, 1962, **XXII**, 197.
3. L. Contu, R. Macolongo and L. Lenzerini, *Rass. Fisiop. Cl. Ter.*, 1960, **XXII**, 718.

The present communication describes determinations of the chemical composition of the isoelectrically precipitated fractions as well as a qualitative chromatographic analysis of the individual amino-acids, derivatives of sugar and lipids constituting the properdin complex.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade. Microchemical procedures were used for the determination of the different chemical constituents of both the isoelectrically precipitated fractions and the corresponding delipidised preparations, using equal quantities for the same chemical estimation.

Delipidisation : Lipid was removed from the P samples (I-IV) as described earlier¹ by extraction with ethylalcohol : ether (3 : 1)⁴ and the corresponding defatted fractions designated as IDF-IVDF.

Isoelectrically precipitated P samples (I-IV) : Total nitrogen was estimated by the method of Nessler⁵, total carbohydrate by the method of Dische⁶, and the total phosphorus by the method of Barlett⁷. Lipid nitrogen values were calculated from the difference from nitrogen values of the defatted P samples (IDF-IVDF). Microanalytical estimations were also performed to determine nitrogen as described. For quantitative microanalysis of carbon and hydrogen Niederl's method⁸ was followed and for sulfur Carius' method⁸.

Defatted P samples (IDF-IVDF) : Hexoses were estimated by Oreinol-H₂SO₄ method⁹, hexosamines by Elson-Morgan method¹⁰, amino-acid nitrogen according to Hawk¹¹, protein according to Gornell *et al.*¹², using albumin and globulin as standard. Tyrosine estimations were carried out by the method of Greenberg¹³.

RESULTS

The various chemical data are recorded in Tables I to IV.

4. W. Bloor, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1928, **77**, 53.
5. Folin and Wu, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1919, **38**, 81.
6. Dische, *Z., Mikrochemie*, 1929, **7**, 33.
7. G. R. Barlett, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1959, **234**, 466.
8. J. B. Niederl and Niederl, 2nd ed., 1946, 79.
9. R. J. Winzler, *Methods of Biochemical Analysis*, D. Glick ed., 1955, **2**, 279.
10. R. Belcher, A. J. Nutten and C. M. Sambrook, *Analyst*, 1954, **79**, 201.
11. P. B. Hawk. 'Practical Physiological Chemistry', 13th ed. 1954. McGraw Hill Book Co. Inc., New York, pp. 892.
12. A. G. Gornell, C. J. Bardawill and M. M. David, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1949, **177**, 751.
13. D. M. Greenberg, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1924, **82**, 545.

TABLE I

Percentage of protein, carbohydrate and lipid nitrogen of P samples (I-IV) prepared from the same serum samples¹

Properdin samples	Specific activity*	Protein	Carbo-hydrate ⁹	Lipid nitrogen
I	101 ± 5	88.2	3.3	0.93
II	88 ± 6	88.9	3.4	0.98
III	65 ± 9	89.1	4.8	1.03
IV	40 ± 10	90.8	4.7	1.04

* In units of anti-C-3 component activity/mg dry matter².

TABLE II

Elementary analyses of P samples (same samples as in Table I) for Nitrogen, Carbon, Hydrogen, Sulfur and Phosphorus in percentage

Properdin samples	Nitrogen %	Carbon %	Hydrogen %	Sulfur %	Phosphorus %
I	15.14	50.13	7.77	1.49	0.99
II	15.21	51.44	7.42	1.60	1.17
III	15.37	49.49	7.82	1.74	1.20
IV	15.51	49.50	7.50	1.28	1.18

In tables III and IV are recorded data obtained with the corresponding defatted P samples (IDF-IVDF).

TABLE III

Percentage of different chemical constituents, like carbohydrate, hexose, hexosamine, amino-acid nitrogen, phosphorus, and tyrosine in defatted P samples

Defatted P samples	Carbohydrate %	Hexose %	Hexosamine %	Amino-acid		
				nitrogen %	Phosphorus %	Tyrosine %
IDF	2.14	1.58	1.80	11.96	1.10	8.67
IIDF	2.53	1.68	1.80	12.22	1.20	8.87
IIIDF	3.05	1.88	2.40	11.88	1.22	8.70
IVDF	3.76	1.48	2.40	12.48	1.25	8.74

TABLE IV

Protein contents evaluated by different methods as estimated in the defatted P samples (IDF-IVDF)

Standard used for estimation		IDF	IIDF	IIIDF	IVDF
Tyrosine ¹³	$f \times 10.2$	88.4	90.5	88.7	89.1
	$f \times 16.0$	138.6	141.8	139.3	139.8
Ammonium sulphate ⁵		88.8	84.1	89.6	90.1
Ovalbumin ¹²		87.0	90.5	96.5	106.5
Ovglobulin ¹²		71.5	73.5	79.3	87.5

f is the chromogenic equivalent for estimation of protein.

The different fractions of P were found to differ very little in their chemical composition although significant difference was found in biological activity. As postulated earlier¹, this may be due to the fact that biological activity depends chiefly on the availability of surface active groups present in the intact quaternary configuration of the different fractions.

The chemical data for lipid-containing P samples (I-IV) reveals a tendency for the carbohydrate content to decrease with increase in specific activity. There is a similar relationship between lipid nitrogen content and activity. The increase in activity with decreasing carbohydrate content is also brought out by the carbohydrate and hexose contents of the corresponding defatted P samples. The phosphorus contents also similarly tended to decrease with increase in activity, as also the hexosamine content of defatted P-samples (IDF-IVDF).

A study of the protein values of the original P samples (I-IV) evaluated from nitrogen per cent obtained by Nessler's method showed a tendency for the protein values to increase with decrease in activity. However, on applying other standard methods for protein estimation, it was seen that there was no marked difference in protein values excepting in the case of sample III DF. When protein was determined by biuret method¹² taking bovine serum albumin and globulin as standards, there was a definite increase in protein value with decrease in activity. It may further be mentioned that the protein values were the lowest when globulin was used as standard in comparison to values obtained by other methods (table IV).

Paper Chromatographic studies (ascending) of the lipid-containing P samples :

(i) *Sugars and sugar derivatives*⁹.—The following sugars and their derivatives could be detected : ribose, galactose, glucose, mannose, fucose, galactosamine, galacturonic acid, muramic acid and sialic acid.

(ii) *Amino-acids*¹.—Both unidimensional and two dimensional chromatography were performed with acid hydrolysates of P samples I-IV. The patterns in case of unidimensional chromatography for both the samples were similar (fig. 1). In case of two dimensional

chromatography also similar patterns were obtained earlier¹⁴ with a standard mixture of known acids (fig. 2—the chromatogram of sample II) showing the presence of practically all the amino-acids usually present in serum proteins excepting tryptophan and tyrosine.

Fig.-1

Fig. 1. Unidimensional ascending chromatography of properdin sample I and IV. Chromatographic method adopted as in the ref. no. 17 after hydrolysis of P samples with BuOH-ACA single run for four hours at 26-28°.

(iii) *Lipids*.—(a) Test for phospholipids: For extraction the methanol: chloroform mixture of Lee *et al.*¹⁵ was applied. The paper chromatography of the extract showed the

14. A. C. Majumdar and R. Sen, *Indian J. Biochem.*, 1965, 2, 58.

15. C. H. Lee, D. N. Rhodes and R. D. Stolle, *Biochem. J.*, 1955, 60, 353.

presence of cephalin only. (b) Test for cholesterol etc.: The properdin samples were extracted with cold ethyl alcohol : ether (3 : 1) for half an hr. The extract was filtered in the cold and the filtrate evaporated on petri dishes. The dried materials were first extracted with chloroform and filtered. The filtrate gave positive test for cholesterol. The residues were further extracted with a mixture of alcohol : water (4 : 1) and filtered. The filtrate gave positive test for phosphate. Portions of residues were first dissolved in water and then the water soluble portions were tested for phosphate and protein. Both phosphate and protein were found to be present in traces. The remaining residues were, therefore, taken up in dilute alkali solution and again tested for protein which was found to be present.

It was observed that there was practically no difference in the distribution and levels of amino-acids in the two properdin samples although they differ much in their specific activities (fig. 2). Figure 1 shows eight clear amino-acid spots in both the samples. However, the application of two dimensional method revealed 19 known acids with 5 unidentified spots in each of those samples and there were no spots for tryptophan and tyrosine (fig. 2). The absence of tryptophan may be due to loss in the preparation of the hydrolysate by HCl but the tyrosine content of the two preparations was apparently very low.

Fig. 2. Two dimensional double run ascending chromatography of sample nos. I and IV. The chromatographic methods as indicated in ref. no. 17 for two dimensional double run.

While tryptophan would not be expected to be present in acid hydrolysates of the properdin samples, two dimensional chromatography failed to reveal any spots of tyrosine also. It was, therefore, thought necessary to investigate the relative tryptophan and tyrosine content of the samples by the well-established method of spectrophotometry¹⁶. Measurements were carried out in solution of the samples P in N/10 NaOH, with and without addition of known amounts of tyrosine and tryptophan. From the results (table V) it may be seen that the tryptophan content is in the range of 2.20–2.30, as found by chemical estimation also.

TABLE V

The values are in gms. p.c.

Samples	Spectrophotometric results				Tryptophan by chemical method ¹⁶
	Tyrosine		Tryptophan		
	Experimental	Calculated	Experimental	Calculated	
I	0.007 (0.006–0.008)	—	2.25 (2.22–2.28)	—	2.265 (2.25–2.28)
IV	0.0075 (0.006–0.009)	—	2.25 (2.22–2.28)	—	2.26 (2.24–2.28)
I+ (tyrosine and tryptophan of known value).	0.041 (0.038–0.045)	0.040	3.54 (3.50–3.58)	3.56	—
IV+ (tyrosine and tryptophan of known value).	0.042 (0.038–0.046)	0.040	3.54 (3.50–3.58)	3.56	—

However, the tyrosine content was negligibly low, being of the order of 0.005–0.01%. From this also it would appear that tyrosine is not a constituent of the properdin molecules, the traces of the amino-acid detected being presumably derived from other protein contaminants still present in the preparation. This finding is of considerable interest for the chemical characterisation of properdin, since so far no purified plasma protein fraction has been described which does not contain tyrosine as a constituent amino-acid.

DISCUSSION

The isolation of P by Pillemer and his group from human serum raised the possibility of its application in therapy as well as prophylaxis as a non-specific resistance factor of the animal system. A technique for the bioassay and a simple method of isolation have been developed earlier² using buffalo serum (part I and IV). It is not yet clear whether P is a single substance of the nature of mucopolypeptide conjugated with lipids or aggregate of isomolecular substances of almost similar structural configuration exhibiting reactivity with multiple substances which infect the animal system. The earlier publications of

16. T. W. Goodwin and R. A. Morton, *Biochem. J.*, 1946, **40**, 628.

present workers provide some evidences of its multiple nature. The present work was carried out to gather further evidences in support of this view. The comparative analyses so far done on the different fractions of the isoelectrically precipitated substances suggest that different moieties like polysaccharides, polypeptides and lipids are shared by all the fractions though they differ in their specific activities. Even the chemical constituents are also of the same proportions in all the samples of properdin studied. The fractions precipitated during the whole range of the dilute acid ($3 \times 10^{-3}M$) i.e., 6-9 times the volume of serum appear to be conjugates of the isomolecular groups precipitated containing different levels of activity attributable to their differences in special configurations. Some physical properties of these samples are under study to evaluate these in relation to active groups through ultraviolet absorption, paper electrophoresis, etc. In this connection it is of interest that the content of globulin is 1.2 times higher than that of albumin when estimated by the biuret method¹² taking ovalbumin as standard and 16 for f . It is interesting also that the value of tyrosine content in the intact protein varies from 7.46 to 8.87. When these values are extrapolated by multiplying these with 16, the chromogenic equivalent for total protein, the protein content of each of the properdin samples exceeds 100%. These tyrosine values suggest that the serum fractions precipitated at pH 5.7 may not be simple proteins but polymers of polypeptides conjugated with polysaccharides and lipids showing the characteristics of glycoproteins conjugated with phospholipids and other lipids.

Contu *et al.*³, however, have noted that there was no tryptophan in their isolated bovine P and it contained only 10 mg p.c. of tyrosine. It was observed in the present work that neither of the spots for tryptophan nor of tyrosine could be detected (fig. 2). It appears that the absence of tyrosine spot was due to its very low concentration as claimed by Contu *et al.*³ and that of the tryptophan spot was lost due to acid hydrolysis. It is to note also that Harriot¹⁷ has shown that the presence of cupric ion as well as tryptophan and other phenolic compounds may increase the sensitivity of analysis of tyrosine by the method that has been applied in the quantitative assay of tyrosine content of protein which was observed in this laboratory also and this may be the cause of the high tyrosine content here. By spot test^{18, 18a, 18b} the presence of cupric ion could be detected in the samples. Under the circumstances the principle and method of Fischl as modified by Inglis *et al.*¹⁹ were adopted for the quantitative analysis of tryptophan and the results varied from 2.20 to 2.30. This presence of tryptophan in our P sample is almost equal in amount to the tryptophan content of ν globulin of bovine serum²⁰ and absence of tyrosine spots indicate that the samples of P are free from any other contaminants of blood serum proteins. It also suggests that our samples of P represent a new type of lipid containing glycoprotein which has not been hitherto characterised in blood serum.

17. R. M. Harriot, *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.*, 1941, **46**, 642.

18. R. M. Rush and L. B. Rogers, *Mikrochim Acta*, 1955, 821.

18a. F. L. Hahn and G. Leimbach, *Ber.*, 1922, **55**, 3070.

18b. M. Yashapiro, *Zhur Anal. Khim.*, 1949, **4**, 199.

19. A. S. Inglis, and I. H. Leaver, *Anal. Biochem.*, 1964, **7**, 10.

20. P. B. Hawk. 'Practical Physical Chemistry', 13th ed. 1954. McGraw Hill Book Co. Inc., New York, pp. 122.

From the data for protein content estimated by different methods, it may be observed that the chromogenic equivalent 16 for total protein estimation as suggested by Greenberg¹³ is not applicable to the estimation of protein content in P because the protein content exceeds 100 in each case; however, more correct results can be obtained by multiplying the estimated chromogenic content by 10.2 which gives almost equal value as estimated by biuret method or ammonia content of the P samples. This suggests that in evaluation of the fractions of protein, especially the blood protein fractions, precaution must be taken regarding the chromogenic value f which is not constant as suggested by Greenberg¹³ but differs from fraction to fraction.

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